

OpenWebSearch.EU

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

Deliverable D1.2
Crawler Coordination Software
Stack & Demonstrator V2

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

i. Project Info

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ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
CERN	CERN
IT4I@VSB	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
SUMA-EV	Suma e.V. (Associated Partner)
CSC	CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy
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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document provides a detailed overview of the second deliverable for D1.2 "The OpenWebSearch Crawler and the Crawling Frontier", a deliverable of the OpenWebSearch.eu initiative, which is supported by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme grant agreement number GA 101070014. It outlines the achievements in developing and launching the Open Web Crawler (OWLer) and its related software components. These are reviewed in the context of their initial proposal stage as a Proof-of-Concept, whose main motivation is to investigate the feasibility of a distributed, heterogeneous and yet scalable crawling system. Our work sheds a light on how a future software system – backed up with more power in engineering and infrastructure – may look like in order to support the creation process of the Open Web Index with the continuous collection of relevant web documents.

¹ Granitzer, M., Voigt, S., Fathima, N. A., Golasowski, M., Guetl, C., Hecking, T., ... & Zerhoudi, S. (2023). Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*.

² Dinzinger, M., Zerhoudi, S., Al-Maamari, M., Istiti, M., Mitrovic, J. & Granitzer, M. (2023), OWLer: Preliminary results for building a Collaborative Open Web Crawler. *Open Search Symposium, Geneva*.

v. Document Management

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vii. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the development of the crawling infrastructure for WP 1 and its current status.

The following key results have been achieved:

1. **OWLer StormCrawler:** A comprehensive web crawler system built on the robust and scalable foundation of StormCrawler running on Apache Storm. It not only emphasizes optimizing performance, but also respects digital rights and guidelines set by the web community.
2. **OWLer Frontier:** This acts as the nerve center of the crawling operations, a repository dictating the crawling activities' direction and pace. It's designed with scalability and efficiency at its core, allowing tailored management of URLs while being respectful to crawled websites.
3. **Architecture & Infrastructure:** The entire setup of general-purpose crawling operates in tiers, notably the Distributed Crawling Tier (DCT) for traversing the web and creating WARC files, as well as the Centralized URL Management Tier (CMT) for managing and coordinating the collaborative and geographically remote crawling process.
4. **Fill-In Crawls:** Beyond the crawling efforts in fetching documents accessible in the vast space of the web (general-purpose crawling), we also employ more structured crawls targeting particular platforms and services, such as Wikipedia, Mastodon, and OpenAlex.
5. **Statistics:** As of the end of August, OWLer has visited over 10B URLs, spanning over 40M unique hosts, in 184 identified languages, effectively feeding the technical downstream pipeline for creating the Open Web Index (OWI).
6. **Monitoring and Reporting:** Tools like Grafana and the OWLer Dashboard provide operational metrics and report statistics to users, ensuring a transparent and efficient review of the project's status and performance.

The realized software and its deployment provide all the necessary prerequisites for achieving the project results as planned. For a detailed list of software repositories and documentation, please refer to the Introduction below.

1. Introduction

As we have come to the end of the second year of the OpenWebSearch.eu project, we would like to present our refined vision and progress regarding the *Open Web Crawler (OWLer)*, a distributed and scalable crawling software system. This report highlights our strategic approach, the technical architecture, and the operational nuances of our tools, along with a recount of their evolution and ongoing enhancements for building an *Open Web Index (OWI)*.

OWLer, as an orchestrated collection of collaborative and explorative crawlers, was created with the objective to facilitate improved accessibility, searchability, and navigability of the Web. It operates as an ongoing development system, focused on optimizing its functionality while ensuring compliance with the digital rights and guidelines established by the web community.

Figure 1: Overview Software Tiers in OWLer crawling system

Initially, Open Web Crawler has been the work title of our derivative of the StormCrawler open-source software, which we have customized to specifically fit our purposes. The environment around this initial endeavor has grown and now comprises numerous complementary system components (see Figure 1). Along the way, we have created five publicly accessible code repositories, which accompany this document as resources:

Zenodo Repo OWLer StormCrawler (for the source code described in this deliverable):

<https://zenodo.org/records/13836849>

Source Code OWLer StormCrawler (including further development changes from the Zenodo Repo):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler>

Zenodo Repo OWLer URL Frontier (for the source code described in this deliverable):

<https://zenodo.org/records/13836904>

Source Code OWLer URL Frontier (including further development changes from the Zenodo Repo):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/urlfrontier>

Source Code OWLer Installation Toolkit (including scripts to set up the OWLer system):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler-installation-toolkit>

Source Code OWLer Log Aggregation (including the Apache Flink topology and installation scripts):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/log-aggregation>

Source Code Crawler Evaluator (including scripts to benchmark OWLer StormCrawler):

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler-crawler-benchmark>

Documentation:

<https://openwebsearcheu.pages.it4i.eu/wp1/owseu-crawler/owler/>

In the following, we will present the main components of the OWLer crawling system one by one and discuss the software artifacts we have developed and our experiences. This includes our derivative of StormCrawler, the URL Frontier as well as complementary crawling tools (Section 2). Furthermore, we want to share interesting statistics (Section 3) and discuss important technical, legal, and ethical considerations (Section 4).

2. The Open Web Crawler (OWLer)

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the various software components within the OWLer ecosystem. These efforts are crucial to realizing the vision of the OpenWebSearch.eu project, seeing that the extensive web data collection serves as the foundation for the technical pipeline that generates the Open Web Index. This data collection involves *general-purpose web crawling*, facilitated by a customized version of the StormCrawler as well as the URL Frontier. In addition, we have implemented several other crawling and scraping solutions, so-called auxiliary or *Fill-In crawls*. These web crawls enhance the general-purpose crawling activities by targeting specific platforms or websites whose content cannot be harvested – due to various constraints – using the standard set of tools.

2.1 General-purpose crawling

The general-purpose crawling system covers the vast majority of the web, tailored for fetching and parsing regular HTML pages. It is designed to function on a highly heterogeneous and distributed infrastructure with machines of different sizes and hosted in different locations. Its modular architecture consists of three loosely-coupled but collaborating layers, as shown in Figure 2. Each layer is implemented by a distinct software stack and fulfills logically decoupled, complementary tasks. The implementation of crawlers and the distributed database system can be interchanged due to well-defined interfaces in the coordination layer. The URL Frontier takes a central position within this ecosystem as its task is to manage and coordinate our crawling activities.

Figure 2: Three Layer System Architecture of General-purpose crawling

2.1.1 StormCrawler

The first layer comprises the StormCrawler components designed for continuously fetching web pages without managing the set of discovered URLs (*crawl space*). StormCrawler is an open-source software project for web crawling built on the Java-based distribution framework Apache Storm³. Storm, designed for real-time processing of large volumes of data, is scalable, robust, and fault-tolerant, making it ideal for web crawling tasks. StormCrawler extends this functionality, and provides a collection of resources to implement and deploy a scalable crawling topology. It allows the extraction of a vast spectrum of data and metadata, supports various protocols, and can be customized to handle unique use-cases.

³ <https://storm.apache.org>

StormCrawler's architecture involves Storm's concept of *spouts* and *bolts*. Spouts are the data sources or streams, while bolts process the input data. Together, they form a *topology*, or a network of spouts and bolts working in unison to complete a task. A critical feature is its ability to scale linearly, permitting a seamless increase in crawling speed based on available resources.

Deriving from the power and flexibility of StormCrawler, we developed our own version, which is tailored to accommodate the specific needs of the OpenWebSearch.eu project. Yet, it inherits the robust and scalable nature of its progenitor, and further extends the default topologies with customized spouts and bolts. To manage and optimize the crawling process, we have fine-tuned these topologies based on our requirements.

Topologies

The configured topologies each serve as a crawling pipeline. Their core elements are HTML parsing, hyperlink extraction, URL filtering, Frontier communication, and caching checks via HTTP to ensure that the crawled page has not been duplicated within a crawling node⁴. It also performs content-based hashing to assign hash-based signatures to URLs and generates WARC files as raw data fed into the OWI pipeline. For more detailed information on the downstream parsing of WARC files, please refer to the corresponding Deliverable 2.1.

In an effort to manage potential security or licensing breaches more effectively, we have instituted a risk-based categorization of crawling pipelines. The following three conceptual pipelines have been developed:

- **Regular Crawling Pipeline**
Designed for explorative crawling, the regular crawling pipeline consumes URLs from the Frontier, follows the general pipeline elements for URL crawling, appends the extracted URLs to the Frontier, and archives new pages. Given its unrestricted scope, it carries the highest risk for security and licensing infractions. Some risks, such as inadvertent interaction with a botnet, are inevitable in the context of explorative crawling. Also, the crawling mode can face requests and/or complaints from webmasters. While we developed a corresponding web page to inform webmasters about our crawling activity and how to control our crawler⁵, exploratory crawling can still trigger requests from the webmaster. Thus, this crawling mode needs a stricter governance.
- **Sitemap Crawling Pipeline**
Unlike the regular pipeline that discovers new web pages traditionally via hyperlink extraction, this pipeline adopts an alternative link discovery method through Sitemaps⁶. These are crawler-friendly tools utilized by webmasters to expedite robot access to website content. The crawler retrieves and parses Sitemaps as well as web pages discovered through Sitemaps. Sitemaps also specify changes on a website and allow for refreshing content in an efficient and timely manner. This pipeline has a lower risk profile as the retrieved web pages are anticipated to be crawled based on the Sitemap mechanism.
- **WARC2WARC Pipeline**
This pipeline assimilates WARC files provided externally into the index and populates the URL Frontier with identified links. This allows to continuously integrate crawling results

⁴ A more comprehensive deduplication is implemented in the centralized URL management tool, the URL Frontier.

⁵ see <https://ows.eu/owler/>, see <https://dashboard.ows.eu/> or see the Appendix

⁶ <https://www.sitemaps.org/>

from external crawlers, most prominently Common Crawl, into our pipelines. Functionally, it retrieves WARC files from S3-compliant storage, parses and extracts the embedded content and relevant hyperlinks, submits the extracted URLs to the Frontier, and archives the WARC entries with slight modification. This non-fetching crawling pipeline hinges solely on already obtained web content, thus eliminating direct risks associated with unauthorized or impolite crawling. For data and high performance computing centers, this crawling mode also eliminates potential security impacts and alarms (e.g. due to accessing bot sites while crawling) as well as complaints from webmasters.

Processing

In deployment, an explorative StormCrawler instance retrieves URLs to be fetched through a remote call to a URL Frontier instance and adds them to its internal task queue. The web pages are then downloaded, parsed, and supplemented with meta information related to the page content. Finally, the URL and any discovered links are uploaded back to the URL Frontier instance, which updates the status of the crawl. These crawlers are lightweight and can operate on commodity-sized machines in any computing center with sufficient external network bandwidth.

Figure 3: Processing of URL items

Thus, a crawling node communicates exclusively with the URL Frontier instance, retrieving and uploading web links (*URL items*; see Figure 3). The communication between the crawler and frontier nodes is implemented as remote calls over a gRPC connection, ensuring loose coupling between

them. They utilize the well-defined Protocol Buffers⁷ API within the URL Frontier project. The URL items exchanged include the normalized plain-text URL, a unique identifier (based on the URL hash), the partition key, and a set of tags. These tags are extracted by the Content Parser or the URL Parser, which internally invoke *Parser Plugins*. Tags could also be provided by users through a future social tagging system, potentially contributing to a higher quality crawl by integrating user-curated meta information during data collection.

Politeness

It is crucial for our operations to maintain a level of politeness while crawling. We ensure this by implementing a delay between fetches from the same set of domains. Despite our stringent policies, we have encountered situations where one of our explorative crawlers was IP-blacklisted by a domain. One problem here is that acceptable delays are not standardized across websites, which requires a more fine-grained level of control, as it is implemented in the OWLer Dashboard. The standard framework for our crawler has operated within the parameter of ten requests per 30 seconds, per domain. Later on, we have switched to a heuristic method of ensuring politeness, functioning more efficiently when the diversity of domains in the crawl space is sufficiently high.

2.1.2 URL Frontier

The URL Frontier (second layer in Figure 2) is the central component of OWLer's general-purpose crawling, serving as the primary communication hub for all collaborating StormCrawler instances. The Frontier software was originally implemented by Allan Heydon⁸ and Marc Najork in 1999 as part of Compaq's Mercator crawler. In 2008, its concept was further refined by Christopher D. Manning⁹, Prabhakar Raghavan, and Hinrich Schütze, who described it as a complex, queue-based, probabilistic data structure for managing URLs in crawling applications. Specifically, this data structure ensures politeness (by enforcing a delay between subsequent fetches of URLs within the same domain) and prioritization (by using URLs' relevance scores to determine their propagation among queues).

In 2021, this concept was re-implemented as an open-source software project by Julien Nioche, funded by NGI Zero Discovery¹⁰. In addition to efficiently implementing the Frontier data structure in Java, the 2021 project focused on developing a standardized, language- and crawler-neutral API. This interface generalizes communication between the URL management component and various crawling tools, including StormCrawler. Given its performance and compatibility with a wide range of programming languages, the author selected gRPC¹¹ as the underlying framework for high-performance remote communication. Our work builds upon the ideas and source code from the 2021 URL Frontier open-source project.

In this context, there was also a crucial design decision to be made: committing to a centralized URL management, with the URL Frontier as the central node in a star-shaped system architecture. We justify this decision in Subsection 2.1.2.1, while the following Subsection, 2.1.2.2, outlines the main components of the OWLer URL Frontier software.

⁷ <https://protobuf.dev>

⁸ Allan Heydon and Marc Najork, *Mercator: A Scalable, Extensible Web Crawler*, 1999.

⁹ Christopher D. Manning, Prabhakar Raghavan and Hinrich Schütze, *Introduction to Information Retrieval*, Cambridge University Press. 2008.

¹⁰ <https://nlnet.nl/project/URL-Frontier-2/>

¹¹ <https://grpc.io/>

2.1.2.1 Centralized URL Management vs. federated URL management

These two approaches represent contrasting paradigms, each with its own advantages and limitations. Centralized URL management involves a single, authoritative system responsible for managing and distributing URLs across a web crawling infrastructure (see Figure 4). This approach is often preferred for its simplicity in implementation and integration. Additionally, centralized management facilitates easier debugging and monitoring since all data and activities are concentrated in one place. However, this model also introduces significant drawbacks, primarily the risk of becoming a single point of failure. Scalability can also be a challenge, as the URL management tool must handle increasing loads as the number of URLs and crawlers grows.

Conversely, federated URL management distributes the responsibility of managing URLs across multiple, independent nodes or systems. This decentralized approach provides greater resilience, as the failure of one node does not impede the entire system. Furthermore, federated systems offer more flexibility, allowing different nodes to implement custom policies or focus on specific tasks. However, this approach also introduces challenges, such as increased complexity in coordination and synchronization among nodes. Ensuring consistency across the distributed system can be difficult, and there is a higher risk of redundancy or overlap in URL management. Additionally, debugging and monitoring can be more complicated, as issues may arise in different parts of the system, making it harder to pinpoint the root cause.

Figure 4: Comparison between centralized and federated URL Management

As we have chosen to implement a central tool for URL management, namely the URL Frontier, we must address the associated gRPC services, which could become performance bottlenecks and single points of failure within the crawling system. However, we believe that these issues can be mitigated by creating redundancy among multiple URL Frontier instances and relying on the fail-over mechanism of the underlying database system. In the end, we see the most serious bottleneck in the vast amount of concurrent update operations to manipulate the crawl space, which can be administered to the persistence layer. Further refinement of the URL Frontier is technically feasible

but is considered a pure engineering task beyond our current scope. As reported in Section 3, the current level of availability is more than sufficient for our Proof-of-Concept, and the achieved URL throughput is impressive given the system's simplicity.

2.1.2.2 Main components

API

The URL Frontier tool comprises three fundamental gRPC services, each implemented as a stub in the Java-based code repository.

- **StreamService:**
Offers the two operations *GetURLsStream* and *PutURLsStream*. Crawlers can call the *GetURLsStream* functionality of this gRPC endpoint to retrieve new URLs to be fetched, effectively asking for new units of workload to be assigned to them. After fetching the respective web pages, the fetch results are again uploaded using the *PutURLsStream* operation. This triggers a status update of the crawl space, in which fetched URLs are rescheduled according to their content quality and change frequency, whereas newly discovered web links are added and scheduled for their first fetch.
- **BatchService:**
Offers the two operations *GetURLsFile* and *PutURLsFile*. Similar to *StreamService*, *GetURLsFile* allows to retrieve URLs to be fetched next and *PutURLsFile* allows to update the status of the crawl by uploading the fetch results. However, in contrast to the first gRPC API, these operations exchange streams of *FileChunks* instead of *URLItems*.
- **InfoService:**
Offers general information on the URL Frontier tool via two operations: *GetInfo* and *GetStats*.

Note that we have identified and implemented two contrastive paradigms of operating crawling software: **stream- and batch-based processing**. *StormCrawler* is a classic example for a stream-based crawling tool, which was originally created in order to mitigate the performance limitations of former batch-based crawling tools, such as *Heritrix*¹² and *Apache Nutch*¹³. Nevertheless, the class of highest-performing open-source crawlers still operates in rounds, i.e. effectively in batch-based processing, such as in *BUBiNG*¹⁴ or *IRLbot*¹⁵. In stream-based processing, a *URL item* is the smallest unit to be exchanged between crawler and URL management tool. A URL item is defined as URL as well as potentially a set of outlinks, which have been discovered on the respective web page during a previous visit. In batch-based processing, however, we decided for a larger, more coarse-grained exchange unit, namely files, containing up to several million URLs at once. This design decision is particularly fit for the class of high-performing crawlers, helping to leverage their potential to generate a maximally high URL throughput.

Scheduling

¹² <http://crawler.archive.org/index.html>

¹³ <https://nutch.apache.org/>

¹⁴ Paolo Boldi, *BUBiNG: Massive Crawling for the Masses*, TWEB, 2018.

¹⁵ Hsin-Tsang Lee et al, *IRLbot: Scaling to 6 billion pages and beyond*, TWEB, 2009.

Each URL in the crawl space is assigned a time stamp, specifying the date and time of its next planned fetch (*nextFetchDate*). The URL Frontier operates continuously rather than in discrete rounds, meaning URLs in the crawl space are not grouped by their crawl depth but are instead ordered according to their *nextFetchDate*. When newly discovered links are added to the crawl space, they are scheduled for their first fetch by assigning them the current date and time as their *nextFetchDate*. URLs are subsequently fetched based on their content quality and change frequency.

To manage change frequency, we utilize the *If-Modified-Since* HTTP field and compare MD5 content hashes from subsequent fetches of the same URL. Content quality is determined using a straightforward yet effective heuristic. Instead of relying on time-consuming content classification methods like Machine Learning models, we use several list lookups. To this end, we have defined *quality lists* containing hosts or top-level domains, which are manually curated and therefore likely to promise high-quality content. As this approach promises high precision on the costs of low recall, it suits the purposes of our Proof-of-Concept well. Anyways, we are covering only a subset of the entire web, and with definition of quality lists we can effectively avoid extensive software engineering efforts.

The current Scheduler component includes the following quality lists:

- **Super head of ClueWeb22:**
This list includes hosts extracted from the Category B (Super head) dataset of the ClueWeb22 corpus¹⁶. Category B is a sub-sample of the larger Category L dataset, particularly focused on frequently visited websites.
- **Curlie directory:**
The Curlie project¹⁷, formerly DMOZ, is an open platform that enables users to list and categorize websites and web pages according to a commonly agreed schema. We extract all hosts from the Curlie directory entries, interpreting them as high-quality content due to their human curation.
- **Outlinks of Wikipedia:**
While parsing Wikipedia articles (see Section 2.2.1), we identified a valuable set of web links listed as references or related literature at the bottom of articles. These links are humanly curated and therefore highly relevant, leading us to assume they point to high-quality content.

In addition to these three quality lists, we also plan to allow users of the OWLer Dashboard to tag websites and web pages. We intend to incorporate this user-generated information into our quality evaluation to prioritize these URLs during crawling. This could help us effectively deliver documents from the Open Web Index (OWI) that are most relevant to users. For more details, please refer to Deliverable 1.4 (Open Website Index).

Tagging & Filtering

While StormCrawler is responsible for filtering based on content, the URL Frontier includes plugin software components that filter links exclusively based on the URL and the metadata of a web page (since the content corresponding to a fetched URL is not known to the Frontier). These

¹⁶ <https://lemurproject.org/clueweb22/index.php>

¹⁷ <https://curlie.org/>

components, known as *URLParserPlugins* (see Figure 3), are used to tag web links. Some of the most frequently used tags are listed in Table 1.

Tag	Percentage
HTML	83.1 %
GenAI	79.6 %
Index	77.0 %
WikipediaExternalLink	48.7 %
SuperHeadClueWeb	9.66 %
XML	1.46 %
Curlie_Business	1.09 %
Curlie_Computers	0.96 %
Curlie_Society	0.87 %
Curlie_Shopping	0.79 %
Blacklisted	0.18 %
etc.	-

Table 1: Distribution of tags (recorded in the week between 31st of July and 6th of August 2024)

The tag GenAI, for example, indicates content that is allowed to be used in the training of Generative AI models, which holds true for around 80% of all crawled web pages. Most of these tags are intended for future *Focused Crawling* use cases and, beyond that, serve purely informative purposes. It is important to note that the default scope in our implementation of the URL Frontier includes URLs tagged as HTML. Focused Crawling distinguishes from the aforementioned Fill-In Crawls, as it is not constraint to a particular platform; however, in scenarios of focused crawling, the scope is adjusted according to more fine-grained properties of the respective web pages. One such scenario is *Sitemap Crawling*, where the exploratory crawl is limited to Sitemap URLs and web pages discovered through Sitemaps¹⁸. We successfully tested Sitemap Crawling as part of a risk-based approach, seeking alternative strategies to exploratory crawling that provide a soft guarantee of high quality (in exchange for reduced coverage) without requiring significant engineering effort.

Logging

The URL Frontier generates a log event for every successfully processed URL that has fully completed the cycle depicted in Figure 3. A log entry is created whenever the URL is returned from the crawling software to the Frontier. It is important to note that newly discovered links are not logged; only those links that have actually been fetched by the crawler are recorded. The fetch does not need to be successful; requests that return an HTTP status code, such as 404, are also tracked. The log entry includes the URL as well as metadata related to the fetch, exemplary in Figure 5. Links that are processed by a crawler, but whose run through the fetch pipeline times out,

¹⁸ <https://www.sitemaps.org/>

are neither logged nor is their status updated. They are simply added again to the queue after a delay of at least 5 minutes.

```
"timestamp": "2024-08-06T09:24:27.164Z",
"service": "urlfrontier-service1",
"url": "https://www.camh.ca/en/camh-news-and-stories/camh-therapeutic-art-project/",
"host": "www.camh.ca",
"pld": "camh.ca",
"partitionKey": 4052993,
"tags": ["GenAI", "Curlye_Health", "WikipediaExternalLink", "HTML", "Index"],
"metadata": {
  "url.path": ["https://news.unculture.ca/p/unboxing-torontos-great-white-squirrel/"],
  "depth": 1,
  "signature": "b8e6b8452ebafe563dff96dccc9585b6",
  "fetch.loadingTime": 836,
  "fetch.statusCode": 200,
  "fetchInterval": 20160,
  "parse.title": "CAMH Therapeutic Art Project | CAMH",
  "lastProcessedDate": "2024-08-06T09:24:27.152532Z",
  "parse.description": "Ten structurally-integrated installations were sourced for the
    two new buildings of CAMH's Queen Street Redevelopment Project."
}
```

Figure 5: An exemplary log entry

Currently, log events are ingested into a separate OpenSearch instance, independent of the OpenSearch instance that persists the crawl space. To extract more insightful information from our logs and to better monitor our crawling activities, the logs are further processed by the *Logs Aggregation Pipeline*. Finally, both raw and aggregated logs are visually presented and made accessible via the *OWLer Dashboard*. For more details on the OWLer Dashboard, please refer to Deliverable 1.3 (Open Website Index).

2.1.3 Persistence

The persistence layer (see third layer in Figure 2) is responsible for storing the crawl space in long-term memory and continuously providing the previously persisted URL items to be fetched next. The underlying database system must handle a high volume of read operations to populate the Frontier's internal queues, as well as read-insert operations to update the crawl space (tens of thousands per second). Any storage backend must be optimized for two key operations: data querying (DQ) and data manipulation (DM), which necessitate a tightly designed data model. Although the specifics of data modeling differ slightly between database systems, it is essential for achieving low request latency and high crawling throughput. In addition to data modeling, factors such as query routing and data locality play a significant role in performance within a distributed setup. The partition key, previously mentioned as part of the URL item, has proven effective in distributing the crawl space across tables and machines, enabling efficient data querying. However, these aspects are not discussed in further detail, as they are fundamental concepts of any distributed system and can be effectively managed by the chosen DBMS.

The choice of storage backend is crucial for the system's overall performance, as it significantly impacts the latency of GetURLs and PutURLs requests. Initially, OWLer relied on the open-source Search & Analytics Platform OpenSearch, which presented certain limitations. To address this, an interface was added to allow for the substitution of the backend implementation, further

modularizing the URL Frontier software and reducing dependency on a single technology. For our current Proof-of-Concept, we decided to use OpenSearch as it is straightforward enough to administrate and provides sufficient performance with respect to the current throughput of URLs.

2.2 Auxiliary crawling and scraping tools

Beyond the general-purpose crawling, we have implemented several other crawlers and scrapers, so-called auxiliary or Fill-In crawls. These collections of web data enhance the general-purpose crawling activities by targeting specific platforms, such as Wikipedia, Mastodon, and OpenAlex. Such websites offer interesting and useful content that cannot be harvested using the standard set of tools. The following subsections dive deeper in the technical details of our additional, smaller software projects for web data collection.

2.2.1 Wikipedia parsing

We developed a Wikipedia parser that processes Wiki dumps which are regularly distributed by the Wikimedia Foundation¹⁹. Wikimedia releases two dumps per Wiki per month, on the 1st and 20th of the month. We have implemented a Python script designed to read these dumps and generate individual HTML files for each article, capturing a wide range of content, including text and tables, while excluding multimedia elements such as images and videos. After generating the HTML, the content is compiled into WARC files and uploaded to our designated storage endpoint at the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ). Our parser, which builds off of an existing Python library²⁰, effectively extracts and preserves most of the structured content on Wikipedia pages, including text, tables, and external links. We developed two distinct scripts: one for analyzing the Wikipedia dumps and another for uploading the WARC files to our endpoint.

In addition to parsing Wikipedia articles, our script also extracts all external links found in the content. These links are saved in separate files, ready for crawling filters (see Section 2.1.2.2) and additional research. This feature enables us to maintain an accurate record of all outbound references from Wikipedia pages.

Our parsing tool currently supports ten different Wikipedia dumps in the following languages: German (dewiki), Spanish (eswiki), French (frwiki), Italian (itwiki), Swedish (svwiki), Dutch (nlwiki), Polish (plwiki), Arabic (arwiki), Japanese (jawiki), and English (enwiki). Each language-specific dump is processed to ensure a broad spectrum of material is preserved and accessible for future work.

In August 2024, we uploaded a total of 83 GB of compressed WARC files, including content from 10 Wikipedia dumps. These dumps are processed twice a month, in line with Wikipedia's release schedule on the 1st and 20th of the month. In addition to the textual and tabular information gathered, our parser identified and documented 6,509,779 distinct domains as external links. These external links, stored separately, provide a valuable dataset for developing crawling filters and understanding the distribution of outbound references from Wikipedia.

For further technical information and access to our customized crawler, please refer to our repository:

¹⁹ <https://dumps.wikimedia.org/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/5j9/wikitextparser>

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/wiki-to-ows>

2.2.2 Mastodon crawling

Our implementation started from the Mastodon crawler made available by the Webis Group²¹. This crawler collects various types of posts – text, photos, videos, and images – and stores them in an Elasticsearch index. However, significant modifications were made to adapt the crawler to our specific needs. Originally, the crawler was designed to generate a monthly index, but we modified it to generate daily indices, to streamline the data output interval with the technical pipeline of OWI running on a daily basis.

Additionally, we introduced the generation of WARC files by adding an extra layer of code over the crawler. This additional layer processes the fetched posts and converts them into HTML format. After parsing, the transformed posts are stored as WARC files, which are then uploaded to our designated storage endpoint at the LRZ. This procedure ensures that the data is preserved for long-term use and future research.

The entire system operates on a Kubernetes cluster, providing scalable and robust performance. Each crawling instance of Mastodon is managed by a separate job within the Kubernetes system. This architecture ensures that the crawler can efficiently handle tasks and recover from potential failures without disrupting the overall system. Kubernetes' orchestration features allow us to easily manage, scale, and deploy our crawling infrastructure, effectively addressing its complexity.

Currently, the modified Mastodon crawler aggregates data from 150 instances, sampled from the top 1,000 instances based on activity and user interaction. This scope maximizes coverage of the Mastodon network. The crawler processes approximately 5 GB of compressed WARC files daily and accumulates 150 GB of raw data monthly, capturing a significant portion of the most active instances on Mastodon.

For further technical information and access to our customized crawler please refer to our repository:

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/mastodon-crawler>

2.2.3 OpenAlex crawling

In order to include scientific publications in the web index, as a prerequisite for e.g. Open Science Search, we harvest data from the publication knowledge base OpenAlex,²² which provides snapshots of its database. To parse data from OpenAlex, we developed a two-folded solution, consisting of a program that converts the snapshot from OpenAlex²³ into WARC files as well as a program that uses the API of OpenAlex²⁴ to incrementally get the latest publications and convert them into WARC files.

For the first part it is necessary to have the snapshot from OpenAlex already downloaded. This can be done by using the AWS CLI. In this case, the program will iterate through the data, which is formatted as gzip-compressed JSONL files. So every line in those files describes a "work" object

²¹ <https://github.com/webis-de/mastodon-search>

²² <https://openalex.org>

²³ <https://docs.openalex.org/download-all-data/openalex-snapshot>

²⁴ <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/works>

from OpenAlex, and from this object, only the necessary information is extracted. This information includes authors, keywords, title, and abstract. The extracted information is then used to construct a WARC entry with a third party crate²⁵. For example, on the 17th of September, around 258 publications were harvested and fed into the indexing pipeline. At the end, the gzip-compressed WARC files make up around 31% of the disk space (117 GB) compared to the original data (373 GB).

The second part – incrementally updating the index with the latest publications – works similar to the first part. The main difference is that the original JSON objects are read from the API and not from disk. Other than that, the work flow remains the same. Only the relevant information is extracted from the JSON object and from that information a WARC entry is constructed.

For further technical information and access to the OpenAlex to WARC converter please refer to our repository:

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/openalex-snapshot-to-warc>

Incremental updates of OpenAlex dumps are a part of our Fill-in crawl library, which can be accessed here for further technical information:

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/openserch-fill-in-crawls>

2.2.4 Further crawls

We furthermore developed tools for harvesting information also from other sources, namely Pangaea²⁶, OpenAire²⁷, Eudat²⁸ and internal Gitlab instances. The process is identical to the second step in the processing pipeline of the OpenAlex scraping tool. Data is accumulated from the respective APIs, and specific information is selected from the results. In the next step, the selected information is transformed to a WARC entry and eventually a gzip-compressed WARC file is written to disk. The only difference here is the actual API access and the extraction of data.

For further technical information and access to available data harvesting tools please refer to our repository:

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/openserch-fill-in-crawls>

²⁵ <https://crates.io/crates/warc>

²⁶ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

²⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

²⁸ <https://eudat.eu/>

3. Statistics

In this Section, we report on statistics achieved during simulated crawls and benchmark tests, as well as during real-world deployment. Both should help to draw a clearer picture of the performance and capabilities of the OWler crawling system, including the Crawling, Coordination and Persistence layer.

3.1 URL Frontier and OpenSearch benchmark (simulation)

This first test aims to benchmark our URL Frontier implementation with OpenSearch as backend storage. Due to its central position in the system architecture, the Frontier’s performance poses a bottleneck on the overall throughput of URLs for general-purpose crawling. It is relatively straightforward to benchmark the URL Frontier and the underlying persistence layer, as the communication with the crawling nodes is well-defined by its gRPC interface, simply substituting a real crawling node with a dummy one. Most importantly, the fetch activities simulated by the dummy crawler have to be close enough to real-world traffic in terms of fetch response time, number of discovered links per web page, etc.

Within the specified test period of 12 hours, a single URL Frontier instance processed 295.9M simulated fetches. During this time frame, the crawl space increased from around 1.5B to over 2.0B pseudo URL items. We chose this “warm start” scenario with an already filled crawl space at the beginning of the experiment on purpose, as it is closer to real-world deployment. During the 12 hours, up to 29.8M URLs were loaded from OpenSearch to the Frontier's local queue data structure. In this test scenario, the entire URL Frontier Java application required up to 80GB of RAM. Figure 6 shows the Grafana dashboard, which monitors the URLFrontier service. At the moment of this screenshot (Figure 6), a consistently high traffic of 2553 simulated incoming and outgoing URLs per second are generated and processed by the respective Java applications.

Figure 6: Grafana dashboard of URL Frontier benchmark with simulated crawler traffic monitoring the Stream-based gRPC service

During the benchmark test, the stream-based gRPC service processed up to 150,000 URL items per minute (2,000 per second). The batch-based gRPC service offered a URLs file with 1M items every three minutes, and processed the corresponding results file returned from the crawler simulator accordingly. This results in over 5,500 URLs per second, hence more than doubling the throughput of the stream-based service. On average, up to 450 bulk operations have been sent to a single-node OpenSearch instance (each bulk containing 2,000 index requests). This number underlines the enormous pressure put on the backend to continuously update the status of the crawl. An important achievement along our journey has been the reduction of this pressure by employing advanced querying techniques. The use of a multi-node cluster OpenSearch system or the substitution of OpenSearch with Apache Cassandra or Apache HBase would be natural next steps to scale up the overall crawling system in the future.

Furthermore, we have created an evaluation software benchmarking the performance of OWLer StormCrawler. During a test, the maximum throughput achievable by the StormCrawler derivate under fixed conditions is measured, using a local proxy to serve all outgoing HTTP GET requests with dummy text. First and foremost, this software helps to validate whether the StormCrawler components function as expected within a defined topology. If this is the case, the maximum throughput can go beyond 100.000 fetches per hour using the local setup.

3.2 Crawling in the wild

Since August 2023, OWLer has conducted around 10.76B fetches (general-purpose crawling without complementary crawls, such as Wikipedia, Mastodon, GitLab, etc.). These web page visits were conducted on over different 40.5M hosts (Table 2). This is a remarkable number, despite the estimated number of around 193.5M active websites²⁹ (a website might be hosted across several hosts), as the frequency of visits is approximately following a Pareto distribution, with a few platforms getting the most of it.

Visited URLs (per day) ³⁰	Up to ~105M / day
Visited URLs (total)	10,757,755,422 until 6 th of August 2024
Unique visited URLs	1,170,925,504 until 6 th of May 2024
Unique visited hosts	40,531,574 until 6 th of May 2024
Number of unique languages	184
Volume of created WARC files	315 TB since October 2023

Table 2: Statistics on General-Purpose crawling (since August 2023)

Figure 7 depicts the distribution of status codes recorded on 1st of July 2024. We see here that most fetches (89.7%) were successful, returning an HTTP status code 200. The corresponding crawl depth is illustrated in Figure 8. Note that we restrict our crawl to a maximum depth of 20 in order to avoid

²⁹ <https://siteefy.com/how-many-websites-are-there/>

³⁰ Note that this number has been achieved during a test crawl spanning 20 days (20.06.2024 - 11.07.2024).

crawler traps, while still allowing for explorative crawling. Furthermore, Figure 9 depicts the distribution of fetch times with an average loading time of 350ms.

Figure 7: Distribution of HTTP status codes (snapshot from 1st of July 2024)

Figure 8: Distribution of crawl depth (snapshot from 1st of July 2024)

Figure 9: Distribution of fetch time (snapshot from 1st of July 2024)

A total of 4.76B web documents have been ingested to the OWI pipeline within a period of 20 days (20.06.2024 - 11.07.2024). During this time, we have conducted a performance test with 10 crawling nodes of commodity size. Since August 2023, we have overall visited more than 10B links in total (see Table 2). This relates to around 1.2B unique URLs that have been visited at least once, spread over 40M unique hosts. Our efforts in general-purpose crawling are not particularly focused on specific domains, yet they are biased by the distribution of seed URLs, for which we ingested previous Common Crawl dumps to our system. This gives us a relatively wide spectrum of fetched web content in 184 languages³¹.

³¹ We use Resiliparse for content language identification:
<https://resiliparse.chatnoir.eu/en/stable/api/parse/lang.html>

4. Technical, legal and ethical considerations

Besides the technical aspects of our work, we have also considered legal and ethical issues while setting up the OWLer crawling system. In the following, we want to shed light on five of our action points towards transparency and legal clarity.

4.1 Incident reporting

Our crawling system contains – as every development and production system – software bugs leading to unexpected and possibly harmful behavior. Especially during the early phase of prototyping, we wanted to actively ensure that complaints about OWLer due to its misbehavior find their way to the developers. Towards an effective incident reporting, we have established *communication chains* across datacenters, work packages and project partners. We found it particularly helpful to agree on technical communication channels (Mattermost, email lists, etc.) as well as responsibilities. This includes the definition of a group of people working in the development team who are able to press the "red button" and shut down the crawling activities in response to reports of acute misconduct.

As we are working with a software system that is autonomously traversing the web in a massively parallelized manner, common issues are impolite behavior triggering Denial-of-Service on web servers or unallowed download of protected content. In such cases, webmasters can exclude OWLer through the robots.txt file (for concrete instructions see technical documentation in Appendix 6.1) or contact us using the email address owler@ows.eu, which is specified in the User-Agent string in the header of the crawlers' HTTP requests. Beyond that, we keep ourselves informed about popular web platforms, on which third-parties can anonymously upload reports of web bot misconducts corresponding to particular User-Agents or IP addresses. Fortunately, we have not encountered a large number of incident reports yet. The major ones are listed below in Table 3.

Affected institutions	Reported by	Time period	Reason
Bank of America	Email	February 2023	Ambiguous interpretation of "Disallow:" rule in robots.txt file
ACM Digital Library	Infrastructure provider	July 2023	Unallowed access of licensed content
Anonymous	Web platform "stopforumspam.com"	June - July 2024	Potential conduct of forum spam from our IP address; <i>Under investigation</i>

Table 3: List of reported incidents caused by crawler software

4.2 Demarcated crawling subnets

In response to a number of reported incidents, we have taken action in separating the crawling network from the datacenter's regular user network. Whereas most compute jobs require only little communication with the web, a crawler usually connects to a large and diverse number of web servers within a short time, alerting the network security teams and Internet Service Providers. As the Open Web Crawler possibly visits up to 100M different web servers per day, it is very difficult to effectively protect against the very small fraction of malicious botnet servers. To mitigate this

problem, we have established – together with the respective network teams – dedicated crawling subnets. Consequently, experts can better explain and justify the seemingly suspicious network traffic patterns of the crawling software.

Another stumbling block that demarcated crawling subnets protect us from, are institutional licenses. Unauthorized PDF downloads, for instance, could lead to license infringements when autonomous software operates in the same IP range as human users. We have committed ourselves to reducing our system's susceptibility to such license issues, which can raise serious security alarms. Thus, as mentioned above, we use specialized crawling sub networks that allows to disable botnet monitoring from network providers and are excluded from institutional access controlled via IP ranges.

4.3 Blacklisting

As mentioned in a Section 2.1.2.2, URL filtering and tagging is a crucial component of the URL Frontier software. This includes most importantly the filtering of URLs based on a blacklist of known Spam hosts. The *BlacklistFilter* component therefore tags links as *Blacklisted*, uses several publicly available blocking lists to identify and mark links. Currently, we rely on the *Ultimate Hosts Blacklist*³² and the blacklists collected by the Université Toulouse Capitole³³. The blacklisting mechanism helps us avoid phishing sites, spam content, and other pages with malicious intent. Consequently, the system is more robust against crawler traps, botnet servers, and similar threats. In our experience, this is an essential and effective measure to avoid unnecessarily drawing the attention of Internet Service Providers, which may be alerted by crawlers' requests to potentially malicious web servers.

4.4 Take-down requests

External to the crawling system, we have implemented the OWLer Dashboard as a prototypical interaction point between webmasters and the web data collectors. A key functionality here is a service for submitting take-down requests. This service allows users to request the removal of specific URLs from the Open Web Index, either directly through the system or via email. Users can provide additional information to justify their take-down requests, helping ensure that content removal adheres to legal and ethical standards. For more information, please be pointed to the D1.4 (Open Webmaster Console).

4.5 Transparent downstream data use

The rise of generative AI tools, first and foremost ChatGPT, has triggered a broad discussion on the web publishers control, in which Big Tech like Google³⁴ and Microsoft³⁵ as well as the content creators tried to position themselves. This discussion was triggered by a widespread concern about the authenticity of web content, which can be – in the times of generated AI – imitated or replicated on a massive scale without the content owner's explicit consent. Technical solutions for this seemingly idealistic problem include among others protocols and schemas for annotating web content. The annotation metadata outlines the content owner's intent on *how* and *by whom* the

³² <https://github.com/Ultimate-Hosts-Blacklist/Ultimate.Hosts.Blacklist>

³³ <https://dsi.ut-capitole.fr/blacklists/>

³⁴ <https://blog.google/technology/ai/an-update-on-web-publisher-controls/>

³⁵ <https://blogs.bing.com/webmaster/september-2023/Announcing-new-options-for-webmasters-to-control-usage-of-their-content-in-Bing-Chat>

data is allowed to be used. Another approach on preserving the authenticity of web content is the detection of generated content. For more detailed information in this regard, please refer to Deliverable 2.3 on the Semantic Enrichment of crawled web documents.

Several studies³⁶ have identified a clear stance against the use in the training of generative AI models, whereas the respective pages should still be indexed by the big Search Engines, such that it remains visible and relevant to users. In order to preserve transparency about the users' intents and simplify downstream usage of OWI, we have derived two flags (boolean values) to condense out of the existing protocols and metadata annotations a meaningful binary signal, namely *Index* and *GenAI*. These flags mark web documents (web pages, posts, software repositories, articles, etc.) as "allowed to be used for web indexing and search" (*Index*) or "allowed to be used in the training of generative AI models" (*GenAI*). Note that the boolean values are independent from each other and thus, all four combinations can appear, whereas the last one basically discloses any downstream data use³⁷ (see Table 4).

Index = true	GenAI = true	76.2 %
Index = true	GenAI = false	0.74 %
Index = false	GenAI = true	3.34 %
Index = false	GenAI = false	19.7 %

Table 4: Refined statistics on Index and GenAI tag

Both flags are present as columns in the resulting Parquet files distributed as OWI. For more information on the Parquet file format, we would like to point you to Deliverable D2.1 on the Open-Source WARC Parsing Pipeline.

³⁶ <https://www.dataprovenance.org/consent-in-crisis-paper>

³⁷ The numbers were recorded during a test crawl in 2024 CW 32.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

In this document, we have summarized our work on setting up the Open Web Crawler during the first two years of the OpenWebSearch.EU research project. The technical documentation as well as the source code can be found online³⁸. In the last 24 months, we have developed a scalable solution for general-purpose crawling which collects web data for the Open Web Index. It is capable of doing so on a vast scale, allowing us to produce WARC files in the order of Terabytes within a single day. This larger software system is complemented by several, self-contained projects implementing auxiliary crawlers and scrapers. Even though the Fill-In crawls run independent from the general-purpose pipeline containing StormCrawler and URLFrontier, both their fetched web documents are formatted in the same manner as WARC files and are digested by the same downstream workflow for building OWI.

The major constraint that we had to face during our time of development, was the limitation of engineering and manpower. For the sake of keeping our work in the frame of a research project, we were not able to walk the entire way towards a crawling system, which guarantees the level of availability required to power an actual Search Engine. Yet, we are now able to collect web data on a vast scale, fulfilling our part in proving that it is technically possible and useful to continuously create and publish a web index as part of a common European effort. Backed up with adequate financial and human resources in the future, the system built so far can be further deployed and maintained. Hereby, it is specifically the infrastructure-related work, which is time-consuming and requires specialized expertise.

At the moment, the current operational status includes three datacenters, namely LRZ, IT4I and CSC, that host OWLer StormCrawler instances on VMs in their OpenStack environment. These are partly crawling exploratively, while some are ingesting WARC files from CommonCrawl as alternative (backup) way of data collection. The URLFrontier as central component is hosted on powerful server machines at CERN. Beyond that, we are prototyping and deploying several crawling and scraping tools at University of Passau. In the future, we will extend our work in creating transparency on our crawling activities through the OWLer Dashboard platform. Furthermore, we will work on facilitating the access to the data products created by the OpenWebSearch.EU project. And finally, we will help onboarding new partners that provide compute resources in order to extend the current collaborative system of distributed crawlers.

³⁸ <https://openwebsearcheu.pages.it4i.eu/wp1/owseu-crawler/owler/>

6. Appendix

6.1 Open Web Search Crawler Webpage

We have incorporated a dedicated page for website owners to understand the functionality and the purpose of our crawler. It also offers the provision to connect with us if they have any inquiries or wish to exclude their website from our crawling process.

Webpage: <https://openwebsearch.eu/owl/>

Content:

About OWler

[Open Source Code](#)

[Data Protection](#)

[Justification](#)

[Your Rights](#)

How to Opt-out

[OWler Dashboard ↗](#)

Welcome to the Open Web Search Project!

We're excited to have you here. Most likely our web crawler has recently visited your site as part of our research project. We crawl the Web to create an open web index and to bootstrap a more open internet search ecosystem, which also includes that webmasters and content producers have more control over how and for what their precious content is used. We've outlined more details of what we are doing and why we are crawling the Web (and thus your site) below, including technical information on how to exclude your site from being crawled by us. It would be great if you would allow us to crawl your site, but it is your choice!

Our Mission

Our goal is to build a comprehensive open web index to benefit all its users. A web index forms the core for every search engine and can be seen as a map of the internet, which relates words and search terms to websites where they occur in. A web index allows users to search and rank websites according to their defined queries. Our index will be openly available to everyone, so that everyone can build their own web search engine.

We hope that by enabling more web search engines, that users get the choice of where to search. Comparable to how you choose your newspaper, you should be able to choose your search engine.

OWLer

OWLer – our web crawler – is a friendly explorer that strictly follows the robots.txt protocol, ensuring legal and respectful online crawling. As we're in the pioneering stages, there may be a hiccup or two along the way, and we apologize in advance for any potential inconvenience. We appreciate your understanding and are always open to feedback.

OWLer uses two main versions of our web crawler: the Experimental as well as the Stable version. The later one is currently built on top of the robust [Apache Storm Framework](#) and the [StormCrawler technologies](#). Beyond that, we are always trying new technologies and functionalities, tested with the Experimental version of OWLer. Here's a brief comparison:

› EXPERIMENTAL VERSION

This version is our playground for innovation. We use it primarily for testing various tools and configurations before implementing them in our main crawler versions.

- *Tools:* Our toolkit is ever-evolving, as we are incorporating different technologies and experimenting with decentralized web crawling techniques to reduce central points of failure.
- *Configurations:* This version also allows us to experiment with different settings to maximize our crawler's efficiency and effectiveness. For example, we might test different politeness policies, crawling speeds, or ways to handle various data types.

› STABLE VERSION

This is the current main version of our web crawler. It includes all the stable, tested features from the Experimental version that have proven to improve the crawler's performance.

- *Reliable:* After extensive testing in the Experimental version, the features and configurations that pass our strict quality and performance standards make their way to this version.
- *Focused on Performance:* Unlike the Experimental version, which is designed for testing, the stable version is optimized for performance. It is geared toward effectively indexing the web and providing useful, up-to-date data for the Open Web Index project.

You can always stay updated about our progress and learn more about our crawler versions at <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler>. If you have any further questions, feel free to contact us anytime.

Technical info

Open Source Code

In our endeavor to keep the internet open and accessible, we believe in transparency and collaboration. We have therefore made our web crawler's source code available to the public. You can access, review, and even contribute to the code on our Gitlab repository (<https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owler>).

Data Protection

We prioritize your privacy. While we collect data primarily related to your organization, we may also process certain personal data. Be assured, this data is always treated with the highest level of confidentiality. We only process such data when it is publicly available on your website and necessary for our project. Moreover, we don't hold onto it forever – it will be deleted after a maximum of 90 days from removal on your site.

Justification

In harmony with GDPR, our data processing is supported by one of the six legal grounds provided in the regulation, specifically protecting the legitimate interests of our project and users. We have ensured these interests do not override your fundamental rights and freedoms.

Your Rights

We're dedicated to protecting your rights. We are currently developing a platform allowing users to request access, rectification, or deletion of personal data, limit the processing, object to the processing, and even request data portability.

Opting-Out

Your control over your online presence is paramount. If you prefer to keep our web crawler from accessing your site, you can do so by updating your website's robots.txt file. Just add our user-agent identifier Owlter, which represent our main and experimental crawler. To prevent any current or future versions from accessing your site, simply add Owlter to the file.

Due to the latest developments in regards to web publishers control, we also support the user-agent identifier GenAI, representing any data use for the purposes of training generative AI models. GenAI is conceptually similar to Google's proposal of the Google-Extended user-agent. Whereas Google-Extended, GPTBot, Anthropic-AI, etc. are data scrapers particularly restricted to power the respective company's AI products, GenAI means to provide a more general opportunity for the opt-out from data use related to the development of generative AI applications. OpenWebSearch.EU forwards any information about the publishers' usage preferences to the users of our web index and all additional data products we publish through an INDEX as well as a GENAI Metadata field, both represented as boolean values.

Please following the step by step guideline bellow:

Guidelines for Updating Your robots.txt File

Adding our user-agent identifiers to your robots.txt file is a simple and effective way to control the access of our web crawler to your site. Here's a step-by-step guide on how to do it:

1. ACCESS YOUR WEBSITE'S ROBOTS.TXT FILE

This file is usually located in the root directory of your site. For example, if your website is www.example.com, you can find the robots.txt file at www.example.com/robots.txt.

2. EDIT YOUR ROBOTS.TXT FILE

Open the file with a text editor. This could be any program that lets you view and edit text files – Notepad on Windows, TextEdit on macOS, or a dedicated code editor like Sublime Text or Visual Studio Code.

3. ADD OUR USER-AGENT IDENTIFIERS

To block our current web crawlers, add the following lines to your robots.txt file. Remember that the matching of user-agent identifiers is case-insensitive, so owler (lower letters) will work as well.

```
User-agent: OwlEr  
  
Disallow: /
```

If you want web page to be indexed in any Search Application built on top of the Open Web Index, but you still want to protect your web data against the use in the training of generative AI

[Media Room](#) | [Newsletter](#) | [Contact](#)

[Welcome](#) [ows.eu Project](#) [Community](#) [Research](#) [FAQs](#) [Events](#) [News](#) [OwLer](#)

```
Disallow: /
```

4. SAVE YOUR CHANGES

After you've added these lines, save your robots.txt file and upload it back to your website's root directory, if necessary.

Remember: the "Disallow: /" line tells the user-agent specified not to crawl any pages on your site. If you want to block only certain pages, you can specify those pages instead of using "/". For example, "Disallow: /private" would prevent the crawler from accessing any page on your website that includes www.example.com/private.

Feel free to refer to our [GitLab repository](#) for any further clarification. If you have additional questions or need assistance, don't hesitate to reach out.

6.2 List of Acronyms

Acronym or Abbreviation	Term
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung
CFT	Crawler Frontier Tier
CIFF	Common Index File Format
CCT	Crawling Cluster Tier
DEM	Demonstrator
DG Connect	European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
ECJ	European Court of Justice/ D6.1, page 29, European Court of Justice (EuGH), need to be double checked!
DSM	Digital Single Market
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
ELSA	Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects
EULA	End User License Agreement
FSTP	Financial Support to Third-parties
GPU	Graphics Processor Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HORISON-RIA	Horison - Research and Innovation Action
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IPR Management	Intellectual Property Management
IST	Index and Storage Tier
LLMs	Large Language Models

LTD	Limited (Liability company)
MEP	Member of European Parliament
MP	Member of a Parliament
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OSSYM	Open Search Symposium
OWI	Open Web Index
OWLer	Open Web Search Crawler
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project
OWSAI	Open Web Search and Analysis Infrastructure
PCT	Project Core Team
PET	Preprocessing and Enrichment Tier
PPET	Preprocessing Plugins Evaluation Tier
RIA	Research and Innovations Action
SERPs	Search Engine Results Pages
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
URL	
VM	Virtual Machine
WARC / warc /Warc	Web Archive Fileformat